

L2-James Webb Space Telescope's Communication Challenges¹

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Abstract—As technologies allow for the capture of photons in greater quantities as the number of pixels on each array increases, the amount of data to be transmitted to the ground also increases. Instruments are placed in L1 and L2 orbits, and L2 is an excellent orbit to perform observation as it is removed from earth and moon light. As space missions explore the outer reaches of the galaxy and for the universes primal origins, retrieving this vast quantity of information becomes harder from distances farther from Earth.

This paper will address James Webb Space Telescope (JWST) past and present experiences in obtaining large amounts of data, 232 GB per day from a L2 orbit. JWST not only is a pathfinder in science, but also in spacecraft communications. The JWST project did not start out with this as a goal, but as the science mission goals became better understood and the existing spacecraft to control center architecture was studied, it became apparent that options needed to be explored.

JWST is the first of a new generation of spacecrafts requiring large data volumes from remote regions in space. With the proper infrastructure in place the search for questions yet to be asked will be possible, such as the origins of the universe and remote planetary exploration outside our solar systems. These issues, and others, will be explored in this paper.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. INTRODUCTION
2. THE ISSUE
3. SHARED OR DEDICATED GROUND STATIONS
4. RF FREQUENCY AND ANTENNA AVAILABILITY
5. TRANSPORTING DATA BETWEEN THE GROUND STATIONS AND CONTROL CENTER
6. RELIABLE FILE TRANSFER
7. SUMMARY
8. REFERENCES
9. BIOGRAPHIES

1. INTRODUCTION

JWST is a large aperture infrared space telescope with a 5-year baselined mission, with an additional 5-years design goal, designated to succeed the Hubble Space Telescope (HST). JWST will continue the HST tradition of advancing breakthroughs in our understanding of the origins of the earliest stars, galaxies, and very elements that are the foundations of Life. One of the goals of the JWST is to observe the first stars and galaxies in the Universe. This grand effort is embedded in fundamental questions that have been posed to NASA's Space Science program¹:

1. What is the shape of the Universe?
2. How do galaxies evolve?
3. How do stars and planetary systems form and interact?
4. How did the Universe build up its present elemental and chemical composition?
5. What is dark matter?

To answer these questions, JWST will be positioned at the second Lagrange point (L2). The Lagrange Points mark positions where the gravitational pull of the two large masses precisely equals the centripetal force required to rotate with them. The Italian-French mathematician Joseph-Louis Lagrange discovered five special points in the vicinity of two orbiting masses where a third smaller mass can orbit at a fixed distance from the larger masses.

Of the five Lagrange points, three are unstable and two are stable. The unstable Lagrange points - labeled L1, L2 and L3 - lie along the line connecting the two large masses. The stable Lagrange points - labeled L4 and L5 - form the apex of two equilateral triangles that have the large masses at their vertices. See figure 1 below.

The use of the L2 orbit on the anti-sun side of Earth affords continuous viewing, easy (direct) access and stable thermal conditions.

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Figure 1 - Lagrange points

The JWST spacecraft is being built and integrated by TRW, the prime contractor. JWST will have three (3) main instruments; (1) Near Infra Red Camera (NIRCAM) instrument (University of Arizona and Lockheed Martin) is designed with Nyquist-sampled imaging at 2 and 4 microns. The short wavelength sampling is $0.034''/\text{pixel}$ and long wavelength sampling is $0.068''/\text{pixel}$. The $2.3' \times 4.6'$ FOV for one wavelength is provided by two identical imaging modules. Two wavelengths are observable simultaneously and the wavelength coverage is from 0.6 to 5 microns (2) Near Infrared Multi-Object Spectrometer (NIRSPEC) is being built in Europe. The NIRSpec provides users of JWST with the ability to obtain simultaneous spectra of more than 100 objects in a 9 square arcminute field of view. The spectra cover the 0.6 to 5 micron wavelength range with resolving powers of ~ 100 and ~ 1000 . (3) Mid Infrared Instrument (MIRI) build by a US and European team. The MIRI will provide imaging and spectroscopy at wavelengths from 5 through 27 microns. The current launch date for JWST is 2010.

One of the challenges for JWST is to substantially increase the amount science data available for downlink for the JWST science instruments, with guaranteed data delivery, and at less cost when compared with HST. The current NASA infrastructure for high data rates user supports Low Earth Orbit (LEO) and Geosynchronous Earth Orbit (GEO) missions. At L2, JWST is not considered a deep space mission, nor is it a LEO or GEO mission. This puts JWST in a unique situation, large amounts of science data at a distance farther from earth. Figure 2 shows at a high level the general data flow for JWST. The existing Deep Space Network (DSN) and Ground Network (GN) do not have the X-band frequency allocated to allow for high data rates from L2. In addition, JWST is also pushing the spectrum limits of X-band and needs to use Ka-band to achieve the desired science data outputs.

Another area where investigations are on going is in the data packet structure and protocols on the frequency. If a large antenna is available and sufficient low Bit Error Rates can be achieved is the standard error correction coding methods needed? JWST will be using Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems/CCSDS File Data Protocol (CCSDS/CFDP) on the downlink to guarantee data receipt. If the data quality is guaranteed and the link has plenty of margin, is convolutional and Reed-Solomon encoding really needed? With no convolutional encoding and no Reed-Solomon more science data can be downlinked over the same bandwidth. The result of this will decrease the amount of contact time JWST will need, which will decrease ground station costs for JWST and allow the remaining ground station resources to be used by other large data volume spacecraft. Of course this has impacts on JWST which need to be evaluated, such as increase power, weight, and heat requirements.

JWST Ground Segment Requirements

There are two (2) overall requirements² that had to be considered.

- Support a data volume of 232 Gbits per day
- Reduce life-cycle cost of JWST

In the current traditional NASA models, which are wide and varied between the various NASA centers and space projects:

- The spacecraft design often dictates the Ground Segments design at will
- Existing infrastructure and communication standards may limit operations capabilities
- Long term growth paths often are not met due to budget or technology issues

Figure 2 – Ground Segments

To meet the L2 communication challenges each requirement is broken down as follows:

- Data volume of at least 232 Gbits per day
 - Review technologies to maximize data throughput both on the spacecraft and the ground
 - Allow for bandwidth growth and review where bottlenecks currently exist
- Reduce life cycle cost of ground segment
 - Review entire system and concentrate efforts where a smaller percent change provides a greater benefit.
 - Review all process early and measure long term impacts
 - Provide realistic communication options for reducing costs, i.e., reducing contact time and bandwidth

To meet the above requirements the Ground Segment teams, including the Deep Space Network (DSN), NASA Integrated Services Network (NISN) and other ground station elements are required to begin ground segment development and to be involved in spacecraft development very early in the process. This also requires that the spacecraft development community accept involvement by the Ground Segment team members and accept some new ways of doing their work that will have long-term benefit. Meeting the JWST Ground Segment requirements will be a challenge for NASA. But this challenge has to be met since JWST is one of many spacecrafts that will be placed farther from earth, with finer attitude requirements, and large data volume requirements.

2. THE ISSUE

There is no generic infrastructure currently in place to support large volume data spacecraft from L2, or other deep space locations. Each new spacecraft pushes the limit higher, but this approach also requires an investment by the ground stations and spacecraft projects for each individual improvement.

The ground stations, which are currently the only way to communicate with space mission generally over 35,786 kilometers, were built in an era when data volumes from deep space missions were small and did not require large contact times. JWST's initial requirement for 8 hours a day for up to 10 years taxes the existing system. This is based on a communication study, 'NGST Data Volume and Communications Study' by John Isaacs³. Not only are the infrastructures being challenged, but also how the costing of this service shall be determined. For a mission on the scale of JWST, the NASA ground networks should be priced at or less than having a JWST built and maintained dedicated ground station.

The Ground Segment team will evaluate many different approaches to meet the challenges of the JWST mission design and the impact of such approaches on the ground system, operations, and spacecraft. To accomplish this, the ground system and other JWST teams will conduct the following trade-offs:

- X-band and Ka-band downlinks for high rate data
- On-board processing of the data to reduce the amount of data downlinked to the ground.
- Antenna size and long term scheduling
- Ground stations costs: leasing versus owning.
- Prioritizing ground transport of data to reduce the total peak bandwidth between the DSN site and JWST control center.
- Spacecraft and operational changes in the telemetry and command data rates, protocols, and system designs.

One approach to bring down the total cost of the system is to trade off contact time, data rates and data volume. For example, the cost of upgrading the existing infrastructure to Ka-band traded against the cost of longer contact times using X-band and the advantages of the various size of the ground station antennas with the possible encoding schemes needed which will impact the bandwidth available for the science data.

The JWST initial launch and commissioning support requirements from a DSN perspective is similar to an earth orbiting system. Once you begin to approach L2 and normal operations JWST no longer fits the traditional spacecraft model for the existing NASA infrastructure, large data volumes, yet not close to earth.

JWST in the early study phases only looked at existing capabilities and what the international partners could provide. But as the JWST mission matures further details on the control center needs, costing, and spacecraft design impacts need to be addressed. As part of this further refinement, personnel for DSN and NISN need to be included early. The DSN and NISN future capabilities, enhancements, and operational experience will greatly influence the type, rate, and availability of the links available.

The ground station challenges can be divided into segments:

1. Shared or dedicated ground station
2. RF frequency, and antenna availability
3. Transporting data between the ground stations and control center
4. Transferring files reliably between the JWST and control center

3. SHARED OR DEDICATED GROUND STATION

Dedicated ground stations for a single spacecraft are often not worth the cost for a short-term mission. But for long duration mission like JSWT the existing per minute charge structure can make building a dedicated ground station economically feasible.

There are few sources for leasing ground to spacecraft services. Commercial vendors such as USN and DataLinks must compete with government programs such as NASA DSN and the European Space Agency (ESA). At the low end is a conservative cost estimate of \$10 per minute for 8 hours a day for 10 years amounts to \$17,520,000. Building or refurbishing a dedicated ground station is under 10 million dollars. If JWST has its own antenna, at least half of the time this antenna is not used. Since the common practice is to use existing infrastructure the Ground Segment group has two approaches: Find ways to decrease the downlink time and make an offer to a vendor with the value of the services for the JWST project (and not his cost). One issue, which is not technical, is the way money is allocated. The building of a dedicated requires spending money in phases C, D, and E, where leasing a ground station requires only money to be spent in phase E. JWST is trying to reduce the costs in the earlier phases, even if it increases the final cost in phase E.

Decreasing the downlink time will decrease the (per minute) charges, however to accomplish this larger antennas and/or different frequencies are needed and will be discussed in later sections. The second item on offering a vendor a price for the service, instead of just accepting his 'per minute' cost has some merit. The vendor gets a long-term contract at a known price. If the vendor insists on the per minute option, the long-term cost is a guess and the JWST project could also look for other vendors in the future who might be offering better pricing terms.

Another problem with using a single dedicated ground station is orbit determination. With JWST, as with other L2 missions, the largest component of the orbital uncertainties for libration orbits is the out-of-plane components. In the past, tracking results from stations located in both hemispheres are necessary for maximum-attainable accuracy in the out-of-plane components. To date, no libration point orbiter has flown without DSN support, or tracking support from both hemispheres. Position accuracy is a function of spacecraft specifics, capabilities, and performance of the specific trackers, and the given tracking regimen assumed (support frequency, durations, distributions, etc.).

The science pointing requirements on the orbit knowledge for the previous libration orbits have tended to be loose when compared with JWST. This will tend to impose much tighter requirements on the spacecraft and ground station supports. This also means that JWST will need to have

downlink opportunity with ground stations in both the northern and southern hemispheres. This creates a problem with building just one dedicated ground station. The use of DSN becomes more of a logical choice.

With the pointing accuracy requiring multiple sites, JWST goal of reducing contact time by using Ka-band, reducing the cost in the early project phases, and DSN upgrading their infrastructure in the coming years to support Ka-band, JWST will be using the DSN as their ground terminal.

4. RF FREQUENCY, AND ANTENNA AVAILABILITY

The RF frequencies used presents the greatest challenge currently. Using Ka-band will allow for a higher data rate to be used, there by reducing the cost of the total ground segment since less DSN antenna time is needed. Other items to consider if using X-band are:

- X- band is supported by all commercial vendors, so backup or alternative sites available
- X-band allocation is crowded and JWST is currently limited to 10 MHz.
- 34-meter DSN provides margin, but would require waivers and additional allocations to get 20 MHz in the X-band

The baseline for the initial design concept for JWST was to use X-band downlink for the high rate data. The initial X-band concept limited the downlink to 10 Mbps. The standard allocation of X-band is 10 MHz, applying for 20 MHz requires a waiver. The 20 MHz allocation can be used for one of these scenarios: First, 10 MHz for data and 10 MHz for convolutional encoding if the ground station is smaller than 20 meters to meet the desired bit error rate of less than $1E-7$ and link margins for all links of at least +3dB in all operating and contingency modes. NASA Headquarters has said that no waivers for the X-band frequencies will be granted for JWST. The JWST project agrees with this due to how crowded the X-band currently is and the amount of data JWST is expecting to downlink to the ground.

Using Ka-band rather than X-band can provide up to four times the bandwidth than X-band for the same ground antenna, thereby reducing the needed contact time. The DSN currently supports Ka-band users in the 32 GHz range, which is allocated to missions distanced more than 2 Million Km from earth (deep space missions) and with JWST located at just L2 it does not fit the current spectrum allocations. JWST has requested to use Ka-band capabilities to be provided by DSN and the JWST request has been forwarded to the appropriate NASA committee. Recently, the NASA spectrum committee recommended that JWST use Ka-Band, 26 GHz or 37 GHz. DSN at the present time does not support 26 GHz or 37 GHz and discussions are currently proceeding studying the

advantages and disadvantages between these two Ka-band frequencies. Either of these frequencies would allow for JWST to have a higher data rate, reducing cost and antenna time needed.

JWST has decided to actively pursue the Ka-Band. Beside the study of which frequency to use, 26 GHz or 37 GHz, the impact of this change on the spacecraft design, power and thermal characteristics is being evaluated by TRW, the prime contractor. DSN is also looking at the current forecast of the 34-meter and 26-meter antenna usage. JWST currently would prefer the 34-meter antennas to increase the downlink rate and BER performance.

5. CAPABILITY OF TRANSPORTING DATA BETWEEN THE GROUND STATIONS AND CONTROL CENTER

The cost of the ground network between the ground stations and the control center is often underestimated during the preliminary mission design phase. In industry this segment, the ground station to control center, can be thought of as a Wide Area Networks (WAN). For the most part organization tend to buy WAN services from an Internet Service Provider (ISP) and communication companies. Managing and engineering WAN's requires high technical skills and to build a WAN from scratch is very expensive. Since JWST has decided to use the DSN ground stations, the WAN services generally used by DSN users are provided by the NASA Integrated Services Network (NISN).

Once the science and engineering data are received at the ground station the data networks need to provide reliable data transfer to the Flight Operations System (FOS). The first problem is bandwidth. None of the current ground stations can provide the science data from JWST to the control center in real-time at the desired data rates of up to 50 Mbps. Both DSN and NISN have plans of upgrading their services to better accommodate JWST and other spacecrafts to be launch in the future, but still not a the real-time rate. The current plan is for JWST to transfer the engineering data at real-time rates. The science data from the Solid State Recorder (SSR) will be sent down via CCSDS/CFDP (see section 6 for further details). All the data will be recorded at the DSN site and metered out at the available line rate. Using JWST virtual channel assignments within the CCSDS packets, the more important data will be received first at the FOS.

JWST will use the existing NISN systems provides the infrastructure to procure larger bandwidths if needed, but areas outside the United States present a challenge. These challenges are not only in distance, but political, network assets availability, technology transfers, and existing JWST/NASA partnering agreements for services. The cost

of the ground network from Goldstone CA to Baltimore is far lower and easier to implement than from Australia. However, all the data from the DSN ground stations will go through JPL in California first before being received at the FOS.

JWST will use NISN to provide data lines between the ground sites, JPL, and FOS. JWST at this time will not be requesting anymore bandwidth than what is currently forecasted to be in place when JWST is launched.

6. RELIABLE FILE TRANSFER

This section discusses the protocols of data from the spacecraft to the ground station, and using a ground network to the FOS center. Transmission protocols are used to exchange data between the Flight and Ground segment. These protocols are implemented on the spacecraft and by the ground segments (see figure 3). The reason reliable file transfer is important to JWST is some of the data on the spacecraft uses segments larger than one CCSDS packet (8k for JWST) and the goal of no science data loss. For example: science observations, a Table loads and flight software loads are larger than one packet. This requires a mechanism to segment the data into CCSDS packets and to be reassembled at the destination. Also, JWST level II requirement calls for reliable file transfer from and to space.

The links between JWST and the ground are point-to-point connections, there is no requirement for routing. CCSDS is the de facto standard in space. The CCSDS protocol is currently baselined by the JWST flight segment to transfer data on the spacecraft between subsystems over the spacecraft LAN. CCSDS is "unreliable" and does not guarantee packet delivery (Similar to UDP). Currently CCSDS is used by many existing spacecrafts and ground stations. Also most of the existing Telemetry and Command systems have tools and software supporting the basic CCSDS protocols. JWST will be using the CCSDS protocol. For reliable file transfers, currently there are two means of transferring file reliable between the spacecraft and the ground station, TCP and CFDP.

JWST position at L2 currently limits the TCP implementation due to delays in the link from earth and the TCP structure. For JWST the round trip time for packet is 12 seconds. TCP uses a sliding window protocol with acknowledgements and amount of buffering and acknowledgement will waste valuable time in using the expensive downlink.

Figure 3 - CFDP Data Flow⁴

The current planned extension to CCSDS is CFDP for reliable file transfer. The JWST project has baselined CFDP for telemetry downlinks and is being considered for command loads. JWST is one of the many projects that are starting to use CFDP and as a general rule the NASA organization will incur the cost in adding CFDP to the ground segment. Of course in full cost accounting the cost is then passed back to the projects, but is spread amount many current and future projects limiting the impact to any one project.

The JWST project also initially baselined the CCSDS/COP-1 protocol for the command uplinks. For the CCSDS single packet transfers this is fine, but for large loads and files perhaps and a better way would be to use CCSDS/CFDP for the uplink as well.

JWST is baselined using CCSDS/COP-1 and CCSDS/CFDP for uplinks and CCSDS/CFDP for SSR and large file downlinks, which will provide for packet retransmissions between JWST to the control center if a data packet is corrupted. JWST will not be the first spacecraft to use these protocols, both Messenger and Deep Impact missions will be using COP-1 and CFDP.

7. SUMMARY

The ground segment is only one piece of the entire JWST satellite project puzzle and needs to be considered early in the spacecraft development. As has been pointed out, the

L2 orbit of JWST presents communication challenges for the existing systems. Early planning and inclusion of the various ground system elements can provide solutions to these difficult problems. A change on the spacecraft, such as changing the spacecraft frequency, can save many dollars farther down the road in ground system, data transfer and operations costs.

JWST will be using the DSN as their ground terminal. The DSN sites fit well into the JWST needs; pointing accuracy requiring multiple sites, JWST goal of reducing contact time by using Ka-band, reducing the cost in the early project phases, and DSN upgrading their infrastructure in the coming years to support Ka-band and higher data rates. We will continue working with DSN to reduce the cost of the ground stations.

The advantages of the Ka-band over the existing baselined X-band are many; higher data rates, lower encoding needs, and reduced contact time to name a few. JWST has decided to actively pursue the Ka-Band, either, 26 GHz or 37 GHz. TRW is still evaluating the impact of this change on the spacecraft design, power and thermal characteristics.

DSN is also looking at the current forecast of the 34-meter and 26-meter antenna usage. JWST currently would prefer the 34-meter antennas to increase the downlink rate and BER performance.

JWST will use NISN to provide data lines between the ground sites, JPL, and FOS. JWST at this time will not be requesting anymore bandwidth than what is currently forecasted to be in place when JWST is launched.

JWST will be using CCSDS/COP-1 and CCSDS/CFDP, which will provide for packet retransmissions from JWST to/from the FOS if a data packet is corrupted. As a risk mitigator, JWST will not be the first spacecraft to use CFDP.

These L2 communication challenges do not come without some concerns, but JWST, NASA and it's partners are meeting these challenges head on.

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9. BIOGRAPHIES

Jonathan Gal-Edd has been working at NASA since 1994. His current assignment is the Ground Systems Lead for the James Webb Space Telescope (JWST). JWST is the follow on program to the Hubble Space Telescope (HST) and is now entering the design and development phase (Phase B). Jonathan was also the Ground System Manager for the JWST flight demonstrator called Nexus. Previous to these missions, Jonathan was a member of the GSFC development team for Earth Observing Science (EOS) information system (DIS). Prior to moving to GSFC from Johnson Space Center (JSC), Jonathan served as the Software Development and Integration Lab (SDIL) Manager, for the International Space Station (ISS) program.

Mike Mooney is a Software Systems Engineer at the Space Telescope Science Institute in Baltimore, Maryland. His current assignment is JWST Flight Operations System Engineer. Mr. Mooney has 25+ years of experience in the areas of satellite command, control, and communication systems; naval combat systems engagement simulation operations; orbital and sub-orbital launch operations; launch range and flight safety systems. Prior to his current assignment, he provided flight software development, ground systems engineering and project management to various NASA missions including ADEOS, ISTP, GOES, NPP and TIMED and DoD missions.

Curtis Fatig is the lead Hubble Space Telescope Servicing Mission Test and Integration Engineer. His team of engineers set up remote Payload Operations Centers, test the entire ground and space software and communication links used for each HST servicing mission, and test NASA institutional upgrades affecting HST. He also supports long term development of new mission ground systems. He received NASA's Spaceflight Awareness Award, Public Service Medal, and many Achievement Awards for these efforts from GSFC, KSC and JSC. He received a B.S. from Salisbury State College in 1978 and a M.Ed. from Rollins College in 1982.